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Does Omnichannel Strategies Matter: A Comparative Study of Millennials and Generation Z

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BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to conduct a comparative analysis of omnichannel strategies of clothing brands among female consumers specifically Millennials and Generation Z in Hyderabad Pakistan. Consumer engagement in the apparel sector has enhanced due to increased digital channels with employed women as a major share of this industry.

Methodology: Qualitative research methodology has been adopted for this study with semi structured interviews with 30 employed women (15 Millennials, 15 Gen Z). An inductive thematic analysis has been conducted of the responses of both generations to conclude the findings.

Results: The results of the study show that Millennials are inclined towards trusted brands and reliability of service, whereas Generation Z is more influenced by social media influencers and seamless experience of retail. Loyalty patterns differ across generations due to varying trust formation and engagement.

Conclusions: A unified approach towards both generations is not a favorable strategy as their loyalty levels differ due to variations in their preferences. Millennials display stable levels of loyalty with conscious approach towards shopping. Generation Z's loyalty is synchronized with the level of engagement they have with the brand. Generation Z displayed lower levels of tolerance for inconsistencies among channels as compared to Millennials.

Implications: Tailored omnichannel strategies are suggested for each generation to enhance brand loyalty.

Keywords: Millennials, Generation Z, Omnichannel retailing, Brand loyalty, consumer behavior, fashion brands.

1. Introduction

Consumer behavior regarding purchase in the retail industry has been significantly transformed in the twenty-first century. How consumers search, evaluate, purchase, and engage with brands is very different from past behaviors. Competition is no longer about product availability in fact it is more about integrated customer experience management. Therefore, omnichannel retailing has materialized into a seamless ecosystem of coordinating stores, websites, mobile applications, social media platforms, logistics systems, and post-purchase services.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

There have been notable changes in the retail sector due to technological advancements as well as consumers change in preferences. There has been a shift from single channel retailing to multichannel and omnichannel retailing. Omnichannel retail combines all aspects of online and offline shopping experiences into a unified customer experience. Interaction of customers with brands with the help of these unified strategies enhances customer satisfaction levels. Retailers are inclining more towards omnichannel strategies because customers like to switch between channels while making a purchase (Timoumi et al., 2022).

Brand loyalty and well executed omnichannel strategies are directly proportional. Brand loyalty is the act of consumers of making repeated purchases from a brand despite alternatives being available. Such customers maintain positive relation with the brand by recommending it to others as well. Existing studies on brand loyalty state that a seamless shopping experience across channels positively influences customer's loyalty and satisfaction (Jo & Bang, 2024).

Consumers from different generations interact differently with technology due to differences in their rate of usage and preferences. Integrated shopping experience is mostly preferred by Millennials whereas Generation Z prefers personalized environment. (Kim et al., 2022). Omnichannel strategies are now critical for fashion brands because apparel purchasing merges consumption, identity, evaluation, trends, convenience. New technology of smart phones and social media presence have increased consumer exposure to digital shopping experiences. However, there is limited empirical evidence on omnichannel practices affecting female loyalty outcomes. Therefore, this research explores omnichannel strategies and their impact on loyalty among Millennial and Generation Z women of a major urban city of Pakistan i.e. Hyderabad.

1.1 Background of the Study

The rapid increase in technological advancement has significantly transformed retail in Pakistan over the past decade. Previously, Pakistan's retail sector was dominated by conventional brick-and-mortar stores, local bazaars, and departmental outlets. This involved face-to-face bargaining and cash-based transactions only. Now the retail industry is shifting to integrated, customer-centered models through digital expansion.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Emergence of omnichannel retailing has become one of the most notable developments. It refers to the strategic integration of multiple shopping channels to provide a seamless and consistent shopping experience. In multichannel retailing, channels operate independently, but in omnichannel retailing the strategies focus on synchronization across all channels which allows customers smoothly interact with both online and offline services.

Pakistan's retail market is the most dynamic one. To reach customers, majority of the local fashion brands are using digital platforms across multiple channels. Consumers are engaged through brand's websites, social media platforms and all online and offline channels at the same time. The term "online product shopping" has become popular because it offers customers the opportunity to browse as much information as they want. Pakistan's retail sector is an early bird in the world of omnichannel however many are gradually adopting this practice (Rizvi, S. M. A & Siddiqui, D. A, 2019).

Customer interfacing technologies which utilize the concept of omnichannel retail enable real time communication between the consumer and the brand. This reshapes the whole retail environment (Roggeveen & Sethuraman, 2020). In Pakistan, omnichannel retailing has grown rapidly as clothing brands expanded from physical stores to online platforms and social media, while e-commerce marketplaces improved logistics and delivery services. During and after the COVID-19 pandemic, omnichannel retailing became essential as brands focused more on online shopping and doorstep delivery.

In Pakistan's clothing sector of urban centres such as Hyderabad, female consumers, especially Millennials and Gen Z, frequently engage with fashion brands through physical stores, websites, apps, Instagram and influencer promotions. This approach makes Hyderabad pertinent for analyzing omnichannel strategies impact on customer loyalty. Empirical research is limited on female generational responses to omnichannel retailing in Hyderabad, Pakistan as most studies focus on general e-commerce topics. More attention is needed to understand and compare brand loyalty among Millennials and Generation Z consumers in the clothing industry.

The study therefore examines omnichannel strategies impact on clothing brand loyalty among female Millennials and Generation Z in Hyderabad, Pakistan. Insights into these dynamics will aid clothing retailers in designing effective engagement strategies.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

1.2 Problem Statement

Although many Pakistani clothing brands have adopted websites, apps, and social media marketing, the effectiveness of these omnichannel strategies in building loyalty among female consumers remains unclear. It is particularly uncertain whether Millennials and Generation Z respond differently to such strategies.

1.3 Research Objectives

1. To examine the role of omnichannel strategies among female consumers of clothing brands in Hyderabad.
2. To evaluate whether omnichannel strategies foster brand loyalty among Millennials and Generation Z.
3. To compare generational differences in responses to omnichannel retail experiences.

1.4 Research Questions

1. How do female consumers perceive omnichannel strategies used by clothing brands?
2. Which omnichannel elements most strongly influence brand loyalty?
3. How do Millennials and Generation Z differ in their shopping behavior and loyalty formation?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study contributes in three distinct ways i.e. theoretical, managerial, and contextual. Theoretically, it extends omnichannel and loyalty literature into a developing-market setting. Managerially, it provides actionable guidance for Pakistani apparel brands seeking cohort-specific retention strategies. Contextually, it highlights female consumers in Hyderabad, a commercially relevant but under researched city.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

2. Literature Review

Retail business in various industries has evolved from choosing to use mono/cross/multichannel strategies to realizing the need for omnichannel strategies in order to survive today's competitive environment. Brands are no longer made by a company, they are merely produced by a company but they turn into brands because of customers in today's day and age. The retail industry has undergone significant change driven by digitalization, technology, and evolving consumer expectations. Omnichannel retailing has emerged, especially in fashion, enhancing customer experience and influencing purchasing behavior. In Pakistan, clothing brands adopt websites, mobile apps, social media, and physical stores to engage consumers effectively. Consumer behavior and preferences have changed due to different generation cohorts and what they perceive to be satisfaction related to any product. It is exactly this preference coupled with the latest tech advancements which gives a brand its unique identity and the rest becomes history either by increasing number of sales or resulting in the failure of a brand. This perceived satisfaction, the very experience of having a journey with a brand during various stages of the purchase, is the culmination of strategies into a single platform- a single entity-known as omnichannel.

2.1 Omnichannel Retailing

Omnichannel retailing has become a key strategy for improving customer experience and building brand loyalty. It connects different shopping channels, such as physical stores, websites, mobile apps, and social media, so customers may enjoy a smooth and consistent experience no matter how they shop. The rise of digital technology has resulted in increase in omnichannel strategies among retailers (Anggraeni, D et al., 2025).

Academic studies state that the connection between different shopping channels makes the customer feel more satisfied and engaged with the brand. Loyalty results from convenience, personalized services and seamless experience across all channels (Anggraeni, D et al., 2025). Shopping is made more convenient and effortless due to omnichannel strategies. Features like online ordering, home delivery and real time customer support are expected by consumers nowadays. Personalized experiences offered by social media help brands build stronger emotional connections with customers which leads to greater loyalty (Laurensia, M, 2023).

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Even with the rise of studies on omnichannel retailing, some gaps are still there. Most of the studies are based on developed countries with little attention towards emerging markets like Pakistan. Study on female consumer loyalty among generations in the retail sector are also limited (Asmare & Zewdie, 2022). While research on generational consumer behavior is increasing, there are still relatively few studies that directly compare Millennials and Generation Z in developing countries like Pakistan, particularly within the clothing retail sector. More work is needed to better understand how these generational differences influence brand loyalty in emerging markets (Souza, 2024).

2.2 Brand Loyalty Theories

Customers who are loyal to brands are inclined to repurchase and recommend brands to others. Therefore, brand loyalty is a crucial goal for marketers. There are several brand loyalty theories which illustrate why consumers commit to a particular brand despite so many substitutes and competitors being available.

2.2.1 Behavioral Loyalty Theory

Behavioral Loyalty Theory considers a customer loyal when they consistently repurchase the same brand over time. This action of repeated purchasing acts as an indicator of consumer loyalty (Abu-Alhaija, A. S et al., 2018). This consistency of purchase reflects habit, trust and convenience. For example, the repeated actions of a female consumer to purchase clothing from Khaadi each season demonstrates loyalty thus highlighting the focus on observable behavior over emotions. This theory is relevant for analyzing generational differences in omnichannel loyalty.

2.2.2 Attitudinal Loyalty Theory

Attitudinal Loyalty Theory sheds light on psychological and emotional ties of consumers with brands. According to this theory true loyalty is depicted by favorable attitudes, trust and preference. This is highly significant in fashion retailing because consumers look forward to self-expression and emotional connection. Positive attitudes with repeat purchases make true loyalty possible (Abu-Alhaija, A. S et al., 2018). Female consumers find satisfaction in choosing clothing brands based on brand image, quality and fashion relevance. This preference and advocacy is seen when a customer recommends Sapphire for its trusted quality and style. This theory is relevant for analyzing generational

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

differences in omnichannel loyalty.

2.2.3 Relationship Marketing Theory

Long-term brand-customer relationships based on trust, commitment, communication, and satisfaction are the building blocks of Relationship Marketing Theory. It highlights stronger loyalty results from responsive service and consistent experiences in omnichannel retailing. Trust and commitment in customer relationships are key aspects of this theory (Sedalo et al., 2022). Omnichannel strategies which provide responsive services and personalized experiences enhance loyalty through strong relational bonds. This theory is relevant for analyzing generational differences in omnichannel loyalty.

2.3.4 Customer Satisfaction Theory

According to Customer Satisfaction Theory, loyalty develops when product performance and service quality meet or exceed expectations. This leads to repurchase decisions and positive brand attitudes (Saikia & Verma, 2025). Focus of present day retailing is to improve customer experience so it may result in loyalty. Repeated purchases are derived from omnichannel convenience, service quality, personalization, and channel integration. Comfort of time delivery, quality products and easy exchange policy are key factors to incorporate loyalty. This theory is relevant for analyzing generational differences in omnichannel loyalty.

2.3.5 Composite Loyalty Theory

Behavioral and attitudinal aspects of loyalty are merged in Composite Loyalty Theory. It suggests that true loyalty is when repeated purchases align with positive brand attitudes (Abu-Alhaija, A. S et al., 2018). Consumers may buy out of habit without emotional ties. Some consumers may like a brand but don't purchase often aren't fully loyal. Legitimate loyalty combines brand preference and repeated purchase. A customer who frequently shops at Gul Ahmed perfectly embodies the concept of true loyalty i.e. repeated purchases and positive attitudes toward a brand. This theory is relevant for analyzing generational differences in omnichannel loyalty.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

2.4 Theoretical framework

Although all theories are essential to understand the relation between omnichannel strategies and brand loyalty among the two generations, however the theory which is most relevant is the Behavioral Loyalty Theory. The reason being that this theory makes the basic framework which supports all other theories like a tree supporting its trunks. This theory puts forward the concept of repeated purchasing habits based on habit, trust and convenience. It then leads to emotional attachment with a brand based on convenience as explained by Attitudinal and Relationship Marketing Theories. Next comes the loyalty based on satisfaction levels which is explained in customer satisfaction theory. Lastly Composite Loyalty theory is a combination of both Behavioral and Attitudinal Loyalty Theory which combines aspects of both. Therefore, the foundation theory of this research paper is the Behavioral Loyalty Theory.

2.5 Generational Behavior

Difference in past experiences, economic and cultural factors leads to variance in consumer behavior. As a result, there is a difference between age cohorts regarding attitudes toward brands, purchasing choices, communication preferences, and loyalty. Age, income, family commitments, digital skills, and technological exposure are the influencing factors. Industries like clothing retail need to recognize these generational differences because in the clothing retail consumer's preferences and shopping expectations evolve swiftly. This is the driving force behind comparing Millennials and Generation Z female consumers by highlighting their differing experiences and expectations which influence their decisions in clothing, digital connectivity and fashion consciousness.

2.5.1 Millennials

Born during 1981 and 1996, Millennials, steer through both traditional and digital shopping experiences. They value convenience, quality and trust. Brands with reliable service, product consistency, and flexible purchasing are the preference of female consumers. Omnichannel approaches like BOPIS (buy online pick up in store), incentives and perks are highly appreciated by female consumers.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

2.5.2 Generation Z

Born during 1997 and 2012, Generation Z, are known as digital natives who are mostly influenced by smartphones and social media. Influencer marketing, digitally engaging content and personalized experiences are mostly favored by gen z female consumers. They are more prone to quick communication, seamless digital shopping experiences. They also favor brands that reflect their identity and social values.

Most prominent form of influence comes from Instagram, TikTok, influencers, peer reviews and mobile-friendly platforms. Generation Z values personalization in fashion retail, trendy products, social identity and rapid communication.

2.5.3 Consumer Behavior Comparative Analysis

Consumer behavior in Pakistan has changed a lot because of digital technology, social media, and online shopping. Millennials and Generation Z also shop differently and have different brand preferences. Millennials focus more on brands they trust. Brand Quality and convenience were also influencing factors for them. Generation Z is more influenced by social media trends, online experiences and recommendations from friends and peers (Sulistyowati, T et al., 2025).

Studies show that in Pakistan, Millennials value reliability and good customer service. They also value long term relationships with brands. They mostly look for information online but still prefer to shop in physical stores. Millennials expect a seamless experience across different channels. Whereas Generation Z is more active on digital platforms. They are strongly influenced by social media content and personalized shopping experiences (Khan, S & Nazir, T, 2025).

Studies show that many younger consumers in Pakistan use webrooming. Meaning they search for products online and then buy them in store. Their decisions are often based on convenience, customer reviews and price comparisons. In Pakistan's clothing sector, features like mobile friendly apps, social media presence and seamless shopping experiences play a big role in shaping how people shop (Khan, S & Nazir, T, 2025).

Current studies focus on generational consumer behavior but there is still not enough research comparing Millennials and Generation Z in Pakistan's retail industry. Available studies focus on online shopping or general digital use. This leaves a gap in understanding how these two

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

generations actually differ, especially in the clothing sector. More research is needed to explore how their shopping experiences, channel preferences, and brand loyalty differ (Khan, S & Nazir, T, 2025).

2.6 Research Gap

Though there are many international studies targeting omnichannel retailing and customer loyalty however research focusing on consumers of Hyderabad is very limited (Riaz, H et al., 2021). There are many studies which mostly addresses e-commerce adoption and customer satisfaction but they lack focus on integrated omnichannel strategies (Afzal, A & Alam, S. S, 2025). There is also limited analysis of generational responses among female consumers in the clothing sector which is a key demographic in Pakistan's fashion industry (Khan, S. A & Nazir, T, 2025). Major cities have been given preference over urban areas like Hyderabad in previous studies (Umer, 2024). Keeping in view the above considerations, this study aims to explore how omnichannel strategies impact loyalty among Millennial and Generation Z female consumers in Hyderabad.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this research paper shows how omnichannel strategies influence brand loyalty among employed women from two different generational groups i.e. Millennials and Generation Z. In this framework, the independent variables are omnichannel strategies because they shape consumer's shopping experiences by providing a seamless experience through different retail channels. This paper focuses on how these strategies create positive consumer experiences by encouraging brand loyalty as well as how they produce different responses among generations. Brand loyalty is the dependent variable. It is influenced by factors such as consumer preferences, digital and social media influence, decision-making behavior, retail channel experiences, post-purchase services and logistics and fulfillment. This framework also highlights the moderating role of generational cohorts. Which means, differences in shopping habits may result in Millennials and Generation Z reacting differently to omnichannel retail practices. In conclusion, the framework of this research paper explains two things. Firstly, effective omnichannel strategies can strengthen customer loyalty. Secondly, generational differences shape how consumers experience and respond to these strategies.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Linking Omnichannel Strategies to Brand Loyalty

3. Research Methodology

This study employs qualitative research approach by utilizing semi structured interviews and thematic analysis to explore consumer perceptions and behaviors in omnichannel retailing. By focusing on experiences of female consumers of clothing brand (Millennials and Generation Z), the research aims to gain insights into their attitudes and motivations, ultimately influencing brand loyalty.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

3.1 Research Philosophy

Consumers interpret omnichannel strategies differently based on age, digital literacy level and personal preferences. This study adopts an interpretivist research philosophy, stating that reality is subjectively constructed which leads to diverse interpretations influenced by individual experiences and beliefs. It emphasizes understanding behavior and social realities from the participants' viewpoints. It also acknowledges that numerical data alone cannot fully capture human actions, which are shaped by culture, emotions, and values. Therefore, researchers engage actively with participants for deeper insights.

3.2 Research Design

This study utilizes an exploratory qualitative research design because qualitative research is better able to capture participants shopping experiences and emotions. Also it will enable to investigate under-researched areas related to female consumer's perceptions of omnichannel retail strategies. By prioritizing insights from Hyderabad, it aims to;

- understand customers' experiences with integrated online and offline channels,
- identify factors that enhance loyalty to clothing brands, and
- compare behavioral patterns between Millennials and Generation Z consumers.

Due to the qualitative design and the small sample from one city, results are not generalizable to all female consumers in Pakistan. Findings reflect experiences of participants within the specific context of Hyderabad.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis Method

The data for this study is collected through semi structured in-depth interviews, thus allowing participants to share their experiences in a detailed and flexible manner. The study focuses specifically on female consumers in Hyderabad, belonging to two generational groups i.e. Millennials (born between 1981 and 1996) and Generation Z (born between 1997 and 2012). All participants were adult females (graduate and post graduate) from the education sector. Women were particularly selected because they play a central role in the country's clothing market

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

and are actively involved in shopping decisions. Only those participants have been included who have experience with both online and offline shopping channels. In total, around 30 interviews have been conducted with 15 participants from each generational group because at this point data saturation is reached. An interview guide has been used with twenty open-ended questions to have a natural conversation with participants about their shopping experiences across different channels. The themes explored in the interview questions were consumer influence factors, digital and social media influence, consumer decision making process, retail channel experience, post purchase service and support, logistics and fulfilment and omnichannel challenges. This helps us to understand what they like, what challenges they face and what makes them stick with certain clothing brands. Responses from the participants will be analyzed using thematic analysis method by (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Figure 2. Thematic Framework of Consumer Behavior in Omnichannel Retailing

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

The potential limitations of this qualitative design are that it is not generalizable. It focuses on a selected sample of women within a point in time. Therefore, its results may not be applicable to the general population as a whole. The insights received from this research are tied to a particular group and city which will reduce diversity of perspectives. Since it is a small sample therefore researcher bias is also possible. Data saturation may or may not be reached meaning some themes may be left unexplored.

3.4 Ethical considerations

This study involves semi-structured interviews, ethical considerations include obtaining informed consent from participants before recording their interviews, maintaining anonymity, and ensuring data is used solely for academic purposes. Participants are free to withdraw at any stage.

4.Data Analysis, Findings & Discussion

4.1 Demographic:

Employed women in the education sector belonging to two generational cohorts have been selected for this study. The two cohorts are Millennials (born between 1981 and 1996) and Generation Z (born between 1997 and 2012). The participants were graduates and postgraduate teaching professionals with relevant experience in their fields. Their need for suitable apparel choices on a daily basis was the reason to consider them as the target audience to interview.

4.2 Thematic findings

The thematic findings from this study show noticeable differences of purchasing behavior between Millennials and Generation Z.

4.2.1 Consumer Influence Factors

The most dominating factor which was influencing purchase behavior was brand preference among Millennials. There was a strong inclination towards established and trusted brands. Factors of lower significance in shaping their decisions were personal influences, peer recommendations and advertisements. Millennials were also more receptive to promotional tactics such as discounts, flash sales, and buy now pay later (BNPL) options. This behavior reflected their sensitivity toward value added purchasing opportunities.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

The strongest influencing factors for Generation Z were digital and social media platforms. Gen Z respondents relied more heavily on online engagement, content exposure, and platform-based influence which was unlike the Millennials. However, some similarities were found between both such as little impact of peer suggestions. Although Generation Z was found to display greater responsiveness toward promotions when compared to Millennials yet they were comparatively less attracted to flash sales and BNPL services. This showed a more cautious attitude toward impulsive purchasing methods. Overall, the findings indicate that Millennials are more brand-oriented and financially incentive-driven, whereas Generation Z is more digitally influenced and promotion-responsive.

4.2.2 Digital and Social Media Influence

Digital platforms influenced both Millennials and Gen Z, with Millennials focusing on convenience and brand discovery, while Gen Z engaged with multiple sources for personalized and integrated experiences. Participants of the survey preferred discovering brands through digital channels rather than traditional means. They also showed openness toward advertisement recommendations and personalized garment customization. Furthermore, Millennials expressed not much concerned regarding the use of personal data by brands, if and when such data was utilized to improve customer experience and service quality.

Word-of-mouth communication and in-store services also played an important role in their purchase decisions. It can be concluded that Gen Z consumers adopted a more integrated approach towards brand discovery across online and offline touchpoints. There were mixed responses in terms of targeted advertisements and personalization, which indicated varying preferences. Likewise, Millennials demonstrated a more cautious approach toward the use of personal data by brands which ranged from positive to neutral and negative.

4.2.3 Consumer Decision-Making Process

Online reviews were a primary source of decision making process for Millennials followed by preference for well-known brands. Trust and reputation were found to be critical determinants in their purchasing decisions. When products were unavailable in physical stores, many Millennials tended to abandon the purchase altogether, although some continued the transaction online which reflected a moderate level of brand loyalty. They had varied engagement levels as their online purchasing frequency ranged from weekly to annual purchases.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Generation Z respondents valued opinions from friends and family before considering brand reputation but also considered online reviews as the most influential factor. Thus social validation played a stronger role in their decision-making process. Gen Z demonstrated higher levels of brand loyalty, as many were willing to purchase unavailable products online, wait for restocking, or postpone purchases rather than switching brands. They had relatively higher engagement in online shopping as their purchase frequency ranged from weekly to six-month intervals.

4.2.4 Retail and Channel Experience

Millennials preferred online retail channels mainly because of the convenience of 24-hour accessibility. Despite this, they continued to favor visiting physical stores for final purchase decisions, especially when product inspection was necessary. Their purchasing decisions were affected due to contradictory information between online and offline channels. As a result, webrooming behavior was prevalent among Millennials, where they first checked product availability online before visiting stores physically to evaluate quality.

Generation Z used both online and offline channels, prioritizing seamless comparison, reviews, and a wide product range. At times, they did face confusion because information didn't always match across different channels but overall they clearly preferred using the benefits of multiple channels together.

4.2.5 Post-Purchase Service and Support

Millennials mostly preferred courier delivery and pre-orders when buying from well-known brands. This shows that trust still mattered a lot to them, even after making a purchase. Overall, their attitude toward online shopping was fairly neutral. However, they really liked the BORIS (Buy Online, return in Store) option, as it allowed them to enjoy the convenience of online shopping while still keeping the familiar option of returning items in store.

Generation Z, on the other hand, showed equal preference for pre orders and Cash on Delivery (COD). Their experiences with BORIS were mixed. Most felt neutral about it, while some had either positive or negative experiences. Since many of them had already dealt with returns before, they were comfortable using both courier services and physical stores. Overall, this suggests that Gen Z values flexibility in return options more than Millennials do.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

4.2.5 Logistics and Fulfillment

Millennials were generally very satisfied with logistics, especially when it came to packaging quality and delivery time. Most of them had positive experiences, with only a few feeling neutral or dissatisfied. This shows that good logistics played an important role in making their overall shopping experience better.

Generation Z had mixed views on packaging quality and delivery speed, with their responses spread fairly evenly between positive, neutral, and negative experiences. This showed that younger consumers were more critical and had varied perception of logistics performance. Due to their greater exposure to digital retail standards and faster service, their expectations may be higher. Overall, logistics satisfaction was stronger among Millennials, whereas Generation Z displayed more divergent reviews of fulfillment services.

4.3 Comparative Cohort Analysis

According to the comparative cohort analysis, it is confirmed that generational differences significantly shape omnichannel consumer loyalty and shopping behavior. Therefore, retailers must design a targeted cohort-based approaches designed according to the unique preferences of Millennials and Generation Z rather than standardized retail strategy may be less effective.

This analysis demonstrates that Millennials are found to be more brand-centered, convenience-seeking and satisfaction-oriented generation with more tolerance towards data usage by the Omnichannel retailers. Whereas Generation Z is more digitally integrated, research-driven, and expectation-intensive with a more cautious approach towards data usage by brands and their omnichannel forum. Millennials value trust, reliability, and ease of shopping, while Gen Z values flexibility, personalization, social influence, and seamless omnichannel experiences.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Dimension	Millennials	Generation Z
Social media & digital platforms		
Promotions favorable, less BNPL		
Reviews + peers + stronger loyalty		
Convenience + comparison + variety		
Hybrid omnichannel usage		
Prefer flexible multiple return options		
Mixed responses		
More cautious		

Figure 3 – Comparative Cohort Analysis of Millennials vs. Generation Z

These findings suggest that retailers in Hyderabad, Pakistan should adopt cohort-specific omnichannel strategies which in short can be divided into trusted branding and convenience services for Millennials and digitally engaging, transparent, and flexible systems for Generation Z. The analysis suggests that both generations demonstrate loyalty differently due to variations in motivations, digital behavior, trust formation, and expectations.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

4.4 Analysis of Findings Linked to Theories

Analysis of findings can be best understood further by linking them to five key theories of brand loyalty. It will help to explain how Millennials and Generation Z develop loyalty differently in an omnichannel clothing retail environment. If we analyze the findings through the lens of behavioral loyalty theory, then Millennials show loyalty by repeated purchases behavior based on convenience and value. Whereas Generation Z displays loyalty which is mostly driven by the digital experiences. According to attitudinal loyalty theory Millennials develop loyalty based on trust and dependability. Generation Z loyalty is based on emotional connection with the brand. As per Relationship marketing theory Millennial's loyalty is built upon a stable system creating reliance whereas Generation Z base their loyalty on responsiveness and engagement with the brand. For millennials, satisfaction is based on packaging quality and prompt delivery service according to customer satisfaction theory. Generation Z's loyalty is based more on a seamless service experience rather than packaging only. From the lens of composite loyalty theory Millennials have positive perception of brands which leads to repeated purchases. Generation Z has a dynamic loyalty system which is mostly driven by experience.

Thus, it can be concluded that Millennials brand loyalty is stable and trust oriented. The foundation of this loyalty is satisfaction, familiarity, convenience and consistent service experience. Generation Z, however, have a robust loyalty system which is shaped by digital experiences and engagement with the brand.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

INTERPRETATION OF COMPARATIVE COHORT FINDINGS THROUGH BRAND LOYALTY THEORIES

The comparative analysis of Millennials and Generation Z across omnichannel retail behavior is interpreted through five key brand loyalty theories.

Figure 4 – Interpretation of Comparative Cohort Findings Using Brand Loyalty Theories

With increase in their satisfaction level and perceived values, both cohorts show behaviors such as repeated purchases, stronger brand preference and commitment. Though omnichannel strategies increase engagement levels of both however they show some differences in how they respond to those strategies which in turn effects their loyalty towards the clothing brand.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Table 1: *Summary of Key Insights Across Themes*

Theme	Millennials	Gen Z	Implication
Consumer influence factors.	Trusted brands.	Digital and social media platforms.	Tailored marketing.
Digital and social media influence.	Preference of digital channels.	Integrated approach, online and offline touchpoints.	Digital engagement strategies.
Consumer decision making process.	Trust and reputation are critical.	Social validation.	Cohort-specific strategy.
Retail channel experience.	Online retail and webrooming.	Multiple channels.	Channel integration.
Post purchase service and support.	Courier delivery, pre-orders and BORIS.	Pre orders and Cash on Delivery (COD), BORIS mixed response.	Flexible return policies.
Logistics and fulfilment.	Satisfied with logistics.	Mixed views evenly distributed between positive, neutral, and negative experiences.	Inventory and supply chain synchronization.
Omnichannel challenges.	Purchasing decisions were affected due to discrepancies within channels.	Preferred benefits of multiple channels to avoid any discrepancies.	Smooth integration across all channels.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

5. Conclusion, Theoretical Implications & Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study can be concluded by analyzing the differing preferences and motivation leading to loyalty between both cohorts. Brand reputation, service quality and convenience are mostly prioritized by Millennials. For Generation Z, omnichannel convenience shapes their loyalty. Though they are active searchers across channels for products yet they also exhibit mixed responses to logistics and service quality. Which can be concluded by stating that they have low tolerance for inconsistency as compared to Millennials.

Millennials' brand loyalty is driven by trust, utility, promotions, and flexible payments, reflecting a value-conscious approach. For Generation Z, brand loyalty factors are digital and social media platforms along with personalization, product comparisons and peer influences. However, there are generational differences in response to omnichannel experiences. Brand loyalty varies among generations. Millennials display loyalty which is stable while Generation Z's loyalty is influenced by engagement and personalization. Hyderabad city is one of those urban centers which are showing a rapid growth in omnichannel retail of clothing brands. Having a large consumer base of both generations with a smaller area to cover, it was relatively easier to approach and conduct interviews of employed women. The apparel industry in Hyderabad needs to implement demographically targeted strategies rather than a unified one. Millennials value trust, convenience, and consistent service. Generation Z is driven by digital engagement, personalization, and seamless omnichannel experiences.

5.2 Theoretical Implications

From theoretical perspective, behavioral loyalty theory is supported by both cohorts. Millennials tend to stay loyal because they trust the brand, while Generation Z's loyalty is more driven by digital ease and ongoing engagement. The findings further support the idea of Attitudinal Loyalty Theory. Millennials demonstrated an emotional fondness for brands they trust whereas Generation Z displayed a greater attachment based on identity and relevance. As for Relationship Marketing Theory, the research indicated that Millennials show a greater preference for dependable service systems, whereas Generation Z appreciates personalized and prompt communication

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

Findings also reinforce Customer Satisfaction Theory by showing that satisfaction with logistics and service boosts loyalty, especially in Millennials. The study also supports Composite Loyalty Theory, linking repeat behavior and positive attitudes.

5.3 Managerial Implications

There are important insights for managers of clothing brands engaging in omnichannel strategies in Pakistan.

- Retailers utilizing omnichannel strategies must segment their strategies rather than applying a uniform model for all. These strategies need to be based on generational preferences.
- Collaborations with influencers, interactive social media content, improved interfaces, digital engagement strategies with flexible return policies are needed to target Generation Z.
- Information discrepancies need to be eliminated between channels i.e. online and offline. Brand loyalty reduces due to inconsistent pricing, unavailability of stock and differences in promotional details across all channels. A smooth integration is required across all channels.
- Since younger consumers have high expectancy regarding post-purchase service therefore more investment is needed to improve logistics, packing quality, timely delivery and customer support.

5.4 Policy Implications

There are several policy implications for the retail and digital commerce sector in Pakistan, based on the findings of this study. Adoption of modern omnichannel retail technologies among local clothing businesses, particularly small and medium enterprises (SMEs) need to be encouraged. Training programs can be helpful for businesses to implement integrate e-commerce systems, inventory synchronization, customer data management, and digital payment solutions

Trust in omnichannel retailing can improve through stronger consumer protection regulations regarding online purchases, return systems, data privacy, and transparent promotions. Regulatory safeguards could positively influence long-term loyalty and participation in digital commerce among Generation Z consumers because they are more sensitive to data usage and privacy concerns

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

5.5 Recommendations

The proposed recommendations, for clothing brands and retailers in Hyderabad, for Millennials are that they need to focus on brand credibility and quality, offer practical promotions and reliable logistics and maintain strong physical store presence. However, more investment is needed in social media marketing for Generation Z so that retailers may deliver personalized recommendations, flexible returns, and speed of delivery. Collectively there is a need to synchronize pricing and promotions, integrate online and offline experiences so that customer support is enhanced.

Future research would benefit by expanding the sample size by including multiple cities. Male consumer's feedback may also be taken as they are also important demographic group of clothing brand retail. Longitudinal studies may also be examined to study how generational loyalty changes over time. A comparative analysis of Generation Z with emerging Generation Alpha consumers may also prove to be beneficial.

From the above conclusions it can be stated that omnichannel retailing is vital for brand loyalty among female clothing consumers in Hyderabad. Millennials are inclined towards trusted brands while Generation Z are influenced more by digital content. Their pathways to loyalty differ, requiring tailored strategies for effective customer retention and sustainable growth for retailers.

5.6 Limitations of Study

For this study has several limitations;

- Reliance on a small sample size from one city therefore the results cannot be generalized to all regions of Pakistan.
- It focuses only on female consumers. Further studies would be more beneficial if responses of male consumers are also analyzed.
- This is a cross sectional study showing responses for a specific period in time. There can be long term changes in behavior of consumers regarding loyalty towards brands.
- Responses of retailers of clothing brands is also important to evaluate what challenges they face in dealing with both generations.

BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

[HTTPS://BULLETINOFMANAGEMENT.COM/INDEX.PHP/JOURNAL](https://bulletinofmanagement.com/index.php/journal)

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BULLETIN OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

VOL- 3, ISSUE- 1, 2026

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